

Dynamics of oceanic slab tearing during transform-fault horizontally-oblique subduction: Insights from 3D numerical modeling

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1. Renewed Dataset of tearing width

Renewed data/Original data/*

2. Renewed Dataset of the models and plugin

Renewed reference model (3327_20) input file:

Renewed data/model_plugin/3327_20.prm

Added initial composition plugin and initial temperature plugin for ridge oblique
subduction:

Renewed data/model_plugin/ridge/*.

You can refer to section 6.2 of the ASPECT manual to use the plugin.

<https://github.com/geodynamics/aspect/releases/tag/v2.3.0>

3. Renewed GMT Script in Figure 1

Renewed data /run_new.sh